

Notes

Metal Chelates of 2-Hydroxy 4-Methyl 5-Chloropropiophenoneoxime

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THE present paper describes copper(II), nickel(II), vanadium(IV) and uranium(VI) chelates of 2-hydroxy 4-methyl 5-chloropropiophenoneoxime (HMCP). Magnetic moments and the number of unpaired electrons have been calculated. The nature of orbitals involved in bond formation and hence the spatial configuration of the chelates have also been established.

HMCP

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the present work were either Analar B.D.H. or E. Merck's guaranteed reagent quality. A specially designed Gouy Balance manufactured by Charis Scales, Bombay was used for magnetic measurements. Powerful electro-magnets were set to produce the desired field. Ferrous ammonium sulphate was used as a calibrant.

Preparation of the Ligand: *m*-Cresol was chlorinated^{1,2} but modification was made with the use of aluminium mercury-couple as halogen carrier. The product obtained was 4-chloro-*m*-cresol (m.p. 54°-56°) which was propylated with propionyl chloride prepared by the method of Brown³ to give propionyl ester (b.p. 245°). The Fries rearrangement gave 2-hydroxy 4-methyl 5-chloropropiophenone (m.p. 66°). The ketone was condensed with hydroxylamine-hydrochloride to give 2-hydroxy-4-methyl 5-chloropropiophenoneoxime (HMCP). It was recrystallised several times from ethanol (m.p. 122°).

Isolation of Metal Chelates: 25 ml of 0.1 *M* solutions of metal ions were diluted to 100 ml. In case of copper(II) and vanadium(IV) the solutions were buffered at pH 5 with acetate buffer while for nickel (II) and uranium(VI) ions, the pH was adjusted to 8 with dilute ammonia solution. 1% ethanolic solution of HMCP was added dropwise with constant stirring till precipitation was complete. Only in case of uranium(VI) chelate it was necessary to boil the solution for about 10 min to get the thick precipitate. The precipitate was digested on water bath for half an hour and filtered while hot through a sintered glass crucible, washed with warm water and with alcohol. The precipitate was dried in electric oven at 120° and was recrystallised from dioxan.

The results of chemical analysis for the percentage of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and metal ions are recorded in Table 1.

Discussion

The copper chelate has been found to be paramagnetic (one unpaired electron). A square planer structure would be preferred by analogy to nickel chelate and further since orbital contribution is not very large.

TABLE I—COLOUR AND COMPOSITION OF METAL CHELATES

Chelate	Colour	composition (percentage)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)	
		C	H	N	Metal		
Cu(MCP) ₂	Buff	Calc.	49.13	4.53	5.73	12.99	1.94
		Found	49.28	4.40	5.59	13.05	
Ni(MCP) ₂	Green	Calc.	49.62	4.58	5.78	12.33	Diamagnetic
		Found	49.42	4.60	5.89	12.35	
VO(MCP) ₂	Brown	Calc.	48.79	4.50	5.69	10.34	2.35
		Found	48.90	4.63	5.57	10.52	
UO ₂ (MCP) ₂	Yellow	Calc.	34.54	3.18	4.02	34.23	Diamagnetic
		Found	34.64	3.30	4.13	34.53	

The nickel chelate is actually diamagnetic showing clearly that it possesses square planer structure. The hexacoordinated vanadium chelate is also paramagnetic for one unpaired electron and the possible stereostructure is octahedral utilising d^2sp^3 hybridization. The uranium chelate is, as expected, diamagnetic.

References

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Reactions of Hyponitrates with Benzoic Acid in Molten Condition

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CHEMISTRY of hyponitrates and hyponitrites is not much developed. From the literature it had been found that reactions of hyponitrates in aqueous solutions have been studied by several workers, but it seems the reactions with organic acids in molten conditions or in nonaqueous solvents have not been studied. Benzoic Acid is found to be the most convenient acid, it melts at 120° and does not develop much vapour pressure. Hence in the present work the reactions of sodium and lithium hyponitrates with benzoic acid in molten condition have been investigated. Presence of many gases indicate that the reaction is not as simple as in aqueous solution.

Experimental

Materials : Sodium hyponitrate, $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$.

This substance was prepared by a standard method. The salt was recrystallised by special method not mentioned in this book. At a time 5 to 7 g of the substance. ($\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$) could be prepared by this method.

It was dissolved in minimum quantity of water and the aqueous solution was filtered through the filter paper allowing all the filtrate to fall drop by drop through the funnel directly into large quantity (250 ml) of absolute ethanol kept in a beaker. As the strong aqueous solution of hyponitrate was heavy its drops immediately ran down to the bottom of the alcoholic layer and gathered there as a separate

layer. After, all the solution was filtered, it was stirred very vigorously and allowed to stand for 10 min. The supernatant alcoholic layer was removed by decantation and 100 ml of absolute ethanol was added, and again stirring was continued till the concentrated aqueous layer was converted into a pulp like mass and finally it fell from the alcoholic solution, as fine crystalline powder. The crystalline substance was washed with alcohol several times, dried, washed with ether and dried again and kept in a vacuum desiccator over H_2SO_4 . The sample was analysed for its elements : Sodium content was determined by converting known weight of the salt into sodium sulphate and nitrogen content as free nitrogen gas by Duma's method. Difference in the weight gave the weight of oxygen. Ratio of the atoms was determined and it agreed with the requirement of the formula $\text{Na}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$. Lithium hyponitrate was prepared by double decomposition between strong aqueous solution of lithium perchlorate and sodium hyponitrate. The resulting solution of sodium perchlorate and excess of lithium perchlorate were removed by extraction in absolute ethanol, so that fine crystals of lithium hyponitrate, $\text{Li}_2\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ separated from the solution. The substance thus prepared was recrystallised from water in exactly the same manner, as with sodium hyponitrate, It was analysed for its purity by usual methods and found to be thoroughly pure.

Apparatus : An all-glass leak proof apparatus, the same as was used earlier by the author² to study thermal decompositions was used in the present study of reaction of hyponitrates in melt. Benzoic acid, A.R. grade, was first weighed in a small tube over which sodium or lithium hyponitrate was weighed. This tube was inserted into another tube having a ground glass joint at its one end so that it could be easily linked up with the rest of all-glass apparatus through this joint. The apparatus was completely evacuated and several experiments were done by taking suitable weights of hyponitrates prepared. The gas at the end of the experiment was collected by a Sprengel pump. The solid residue was weighed and treated first with benzene to remove unreacted benzoic acid and then with water. The aqueous extract was analysed for nitrite, benzoate and nitrate contents after first performing qualitative tests : the gaseous mixture was analysed for nitric oxide, nitrous oxide and free nitrogen. The results are given in the accompanying Tables A and B.

Discussion

The results of the analysis of solid residue and gaseous products indicate that the reaction in molten benzoic acid medium proceeds in a manner different from that in aqueous media. It was found that all the nitrogen of the sodium hyponitrate was almost quantitatively displaced as nitric oxide and no nitrogen was left in the solid. This observation was made by previous workers^{3,4}. The nitrite is always formed in a large quantity during the reaction. Presence of many gases indicate that the reaction is not as simple as in aqueous solution. The presence of N_2O_3 in very small amounts was detected only